

SHEARLET FEATURES FOR REGISTRATION OF REMOTELY SENSED MULTITEMPORAL IMAGES

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ABSTRACT

We investigate the role of anisotropic feature extraction methods for automatic image registration of remotely sensed multitemporal images. Building on the classical use of wavelets in image registration, we develop an algorithm based on shearlets, a mathematical generalization of wavelets that offers increased directional sensitivity. Experimental results on multitemporal Landsat images are presented, which indicate superior performance of the shearlet algorithm when compared to classical wavelet algorithms.

Index Terms— Image registration, shearlets, wavelets, multitemporal images, Landsat.

1 INTRODUCTION

The problem of accurately and robustly registering multitemporal image data is a significant problem in the field of remote sensing. Images of the same scene, captured by the same sensor, can have severe misalignment if taken at different times. This can be due to seasonal changes, cloud coverage, and differences in sensor placement. In order to register two such scenes, techniques developed from the mathematical discipline of harmonic analysis have been successful.

In particular, methods based on *wavelets* have been effectively applied to the problem of registering multitemporal, remotely-sensed images [1]. By decomposing an image according to a discrete wavelet algorithm, an image is reduced to more essential features, which are easier to match. It is well-known that wavelets capture certain features of an image, such as textures, quite well. Their simple and fast implementation through a variety of filter schemes has also contributed to the success of wavelets and related algorithms, such as Simoncelli steerable filters [2].

However, wavelets are known to be *isotropic*, meaning they do not effectively represent images that have di-

rectional features. This theoretical limitation to wavelets has been known since the beginning of their study [3], and puts limitations on their effectiveness in analyzing certain image classes. In particular, images with strong edge-like features, including rivers, roads, and mountains, are not optimally represented with wavelet-like algorithms.

Anisotropic generalizations of wavelets abound. In particular, *shearlets* [4], [5] give a fast, optimized, and directionally-dependent decomposition of images, which we shall show yield a robust algorithm for the registration of multitemporal images.

2 BACKGROUND ON WAVELETS AND SHEARLETS

In a broad sense, wavelet algorithms decompose an image with respect to *scale* and *translation*. Mathematically, for a signal $f \in L^2([0, 1]^2)$, understood as an ideal image signal, and an appropriately chosen wavelet function ψ , f may be decomposed as

$$f \sim \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z}^2} \langle f, \Psi_{m,n} \rangle \Psi_{m,n},$$

where:

- $\Psi_{m,n}(x) = 2^{\frac{m}{2}} \psi(A^m x - n)$,
- $A = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$.

The collection of wavelet coefficients $\{\langle f, \Psi_{m,n} \rangle\}_{m \in \mathbb{Z}, n \in \mathbb{Z}^2}$ describes the behavior of f , our image signal, at different scales (determined by m) and at different translations (determined by n). This continuous scheme is discretized to work with real, discrete image signals.

Shearlets generalize wavelets by decomposing with respect not just to *scale* and *translation*, but also *direction*. Mathematically, given a signal $f \in L^2([0, 1]^2)$ and an appropriate base function ψ , we may decompose f as

$$f \sim \sum_{i=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{j=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}^2} \langle f, \Psi_{i,j,k} \rangle \Psi_{i,j,k},$$

where:

- $\Psi_{i,j,k}(x) = 2^{\frac{3i}{4}} \Psi(B^j A^i x - k),$
- $A = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 2^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{pmatrix}, B = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$

The matrix A is now anisotropic, which will prioritize certain directions. The new matrix B is a shearing matrix, and it determines this prioritized direction. The shearlet coefficients $\{\langle f, \Psi_{i,j,k} \rangle\}_{i,j \in \mathbb{Z}, k \in \mathbb{Z}^2}$ describe the behavior of f at different scales (determined by i), translations (determined by k) and directions (determined by j). Shearlets have been successfully deployed for image denoising [6] and superresolution of remotely sensed data [7].

The role of shearlets in automatic image registration can be understood heuristically as follows: shearlets produce sparse, concentrated, and directional features in images, which give the optimization algorithm used for image registration sparse, concentrated features with which to match.

We hypothesized these sparse, concentrated features would allow us to register multitemporal images that begin severely misaligned. More precisely, we hypothesized the sparsity of our shearlet features would produce a more robust registration algorithm, compared to one based on classical wavelets. Experimental results confirming this heuristic argument are discussed in Section 4.

3 REGISTRATION ALGORITHM DESIGN

Our image registration algorithm is based on decomposing the input and reference images using harmonic analysis tools. Our ambition is to compare isotropic wavelet-like methods to an anisotropic generalization, shearlets. To do so, we consider wavelet-like algorithms in the form of spline wavelets and Simoncelli steerable pyramids [8], and the fast finite shearlet transform (FFST) [9]. These features are then matched using a non-linear least squares optimization algorithm, in order to compute the registration transformation between the images.

We summarize our image registration algorithm in terms of the four components of image registration described by Brown [10]:

1. *Search Space:* Rotation and translation (RT).
2. *Features:* Wavelet features in one case and shearlet features in another.
3. *Similarity Metric:* Unconstrained least squares. That is, if F_R and F_I are the reference and input features, N the number of relevant pixels, (x_i, y_i) the integer coordinate of the i th pixel, and T_p the transformation associated to parameters registration p , we seek to minimize the similarity metric given by:

$$\chi^2(p) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (F_R(T_p(x_i, y_i)) - F_I(x_i, y_i))^2.$$

4. *Search Strategy:* Modified Marquadt-Levenberg method of solving non-linear least squares problems [11], [12].

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To test our wavelet and shearlet algorithms, we registered multitemporal images produced by Landsat-7 ETM+ and Landsat-5 TM sensors. These images are of the Chesapeake Bay (eastern USA) and have been processed by USGS EROS Data Center, by removing artifacts and resampling. The Landsat-7 ETM+ image was captured in 1999 and the Landsat-5 TM image was captured in 1997. The images may be seen in Figure 1. Notice the large displacement between the two images. Indeed, using ENVI software tools, manual registration was performed on the images to compute an RT transformation between them. The manual registration parameters are: $(T_x, T_y, \theta) = (103.2, -8.1, 0)$. This means to recover the reference image from input image, one must translate the input image 103.2 pixels to the right (positive x direction) and 8.1 pixels down (negative y direction), with no rotation required. This is an exceptionally large translation in the x direction, so this image pair constitutes a severe misalignment.

We performed automatic image registration with wavelet-like features and shearlet features, and compared the results to this manual registration. Our goal was to study the robustness of the registration algorithms, and in particular, whether using anisotropic shearlet features improved robustness, when compared to isotropic wavelet features. To evaluate the robustness

Fig. 1. Input (top) and reference (bottom) multitemporal images. The images are 256×256 scenes from band 4 of a Landsat-7 ETM+ and Landsat-5 TM, respectively.

of our algorithms, we allowed the initial guess of the registration, denoted $(T_{x_0}, T_{y_0}, \theta_0)$, to increase towards the truth registration. By starting far away and moving towards the correct registration, we analyze how far the initial guess could be from the truth registration and still acquire accurate registration. A more robust algorithm will allow for a poorer initial guess, while still retaining accurate registration. The results of our registration experiments may be seen in Tables 1, 2, 3, 4.

Tables 1 and 2 indicate the superior robustness of shearlets when compared to spline wavelets or Simoncelli band-pass features. Table 3 is ambiguous as to which of shearlets or Simoncelli low-pass is more ro-

$(T_{x_0}, T_{y_0}, \theta_0)$	Spline Wavelets	Shearlets
(0,0,0)	(-1.5, 1.1, -2.4)	(-.1, .3, .1)
(10, -1, 0)	(10.2, -.6, .1)	(62.6, 33.1, 8.54)
(20, -2, 0)	(18.4, -1.8, -1.0)	(64.8, 30.3, .1)
(30, -3, 0)	(29.6, -2.7, -2)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(40, -4, 0)	(39.3, -4.5, -1.3)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(50, -5, 0)	(39.3, 4.0, -1.3)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(60, -6, 0)	(62.9, -1.0, -.1)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(70, -7, 0)	(70.9, -.2, -1.2)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(80, -8, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, 0)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(90, -9, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, 0)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(100, -10, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, 0)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)

Table 1. Comparison of spline wavelets to shearlets. Bold entries indicate convergent registrations. The spline wavelets algorithm begins to converge at $(80, -8, 0)$, the shearlets algorithm at $(30, -3, 0)$.

bust for these multitemporal images, but more refined choices of initial guesses in Table 4 indicate the superior robustness of shearlets in this case as well.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In our experiments, shearlet-based registration outperformed wavelet-based registration in terms of algorithm robustness. When compared to spline wavelets and Simoncelli band-pass filters, shearlet features provide an overwhelmingly more robust method for registration, allowing a far poorer initial registration guess. Indeed, shearlet features allow for an initial guess that is at least twice as poor in terms of distance from the truth registration. Simoncelli low-pass features are more comparable to shearlets, but shearlets are slightly superior in this case as well.

It is of interest to test this method on additional multitemporal images, including those with radically different image content, such as varied cloud coverage.

6 References

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$(T_{x_0}, T_{y_0}, \theta_0)$	Sim.-Band	Shearlets
(0,0,0)	(.5, 3.4 -6.6)	(-.1, .3, .1)
(10,-1, 0)	(10.8, 14.9, -4.5)	(62.6, 33.1, 8.54)
(20, -2, 0)	(10.8, 14.8, -4.6)	(64.8, 30.3, .1)
(30, -3, 0)	(30.1, -3.0, 0)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(40, -4, 0)	(42.3, -1.8, -13.3)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(50, -5, 0)	(48.1, 4.9, -3.8)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(60, -6, 0)	(61.3, -1.2, .6)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(70, -7, 0)	(60.8, 12.8, .8)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(80, -8, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, .1)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(90, -9, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, .1)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(100, -10, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, .1)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)

Table 2. Comparison of Simoncelli band-pass features to shearlets. Bold entries indicate convergent registrations. The Simoncelli band-pass algorithm begins to converge at (80, -8, 0), the shearlets algorithm at (30, -3, 0).

$(T_{x_0}, T_{y_0}, \theta_0)$	Sim.-Low	Shearlets
(0,0,0)	(-12.2, 2.2, -14.7)	(-.1, .3, .1)
(10, -1, 0)	(19.2, 6.8, -10.0)	(62.6, 33.1, 8.54)
(20, -2, 0)	(41.9, -.9, -12.3)	(64.8, 30.3, .1)
(30, -3, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, .1)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(40, -4, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, .1)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(50, -5, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, .1)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(60, -6, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, .1)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(70, -7, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, .1)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(80, -8, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, .1)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(90, -9, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, .1)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)
(100, -10, 0)	(103.5, -8.0, .1)	(103.6, -8.2, .1)

Table 3. Comparison of Simoncelli low-pass features to shearlets, first analysis. Bold entries indicate convergent registrations. Both the Simoncelli low-pass algorithm and the shearlets algorithm begin to converge at (30, -3, 0). It is thus ambiguous which set of features are more robust.

$(T_{x_0}, T_{y_0}, \theta_0)$	Sim.-Low	Shearlets
(5, -8, .0)	(-8.0, -10.9, -12.2)	(103.6, -8.1, 0)
(10, -8, 0)	(-13.5, 2.1, -14.6)	(103.6, -8.2, 0)
(20, -8, 0)	(14.5, -8.3, -2.6)	(103.6, -8.2, 0)

Table 4. Comparison of Simoncelli low-pass features to shearlets, second analysis. Bold entries indicate convergent registrations. When the T_{y_0} parameter is fixed near the correct value, shearlets have superior robustness near the critical threshold of $T_{x_0} = 30$.

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